

THE ROLE OF THE CLUSTER IN THE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the consideration of management issues based on the role of the cluster in the construction complex and its approach. The concept of a cluster is analyzed and the definition of the cluster approach is revealed. The current situation in the construction industry has been studied and the need to use clustering of construction enterprises as a mechanism for effective cooperation between enterprises has been substantiated.*

Keywords: *cluster, competition, innovation, project, competitiveness, value chain, design, construction industry, construction products, investor.*

Introduction: One of the drivers of the networks that currently develop the economy of the territory is construction. In terms of the qualitative development of the construction network in the regions, innovative measures are being carried out to achieve results today.

As one of the priorities of state policy today in the regions is the effective management of construction on the basis of cluster development in the construction complex.

A number of measures have been carried out to reform the construction sector, and the state management system in the field has been radically improved. As a result, a digitization system was introduced to ensure transparency in the industry. The electronic rating system of the project and contracting organizations was launched and the implementation of public procurement (tenders) in electronic form online was established.

To this end, we have built nearly 300,000 housing units across our country in the last six years, or 10 times more than in previous years [1].

The decrees of President №-60 of January 28, 2022 “On the development strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” are evidence that the ground is being laid for the adequate development of the construction production process in our Republic today.

Analysis of thematic literature: The construction complex plays a very important role in the development of the economy of the state, which in turn consists of the economy of individual regions of the country. It is one of the main, fund-forming sectors that largely determine the pace of development of the region's economy. In the following years, the independence of the areas where responsibility for the results of economic development has increased.

A building complex is an organized system of enterprises and industries, combined with stable production, technological and economic ties in the creation of building products. The construction complex carries out a whole cycle of work, from the design of building objects to their commissioning with a building base and the production of special types of material resources. The building complex includes construction, construction structures and the building materials industry. So, in order to organize effective management in the construction complex, the requirement of the present day is to establish a cluster in the construction complex.

In the current conditions, a set of enterprises based on the territorial association of raw materials suppliers and finished products manufacturers connected by a technological chain, territorial clusters combining a group of interconnected networks are an important form of cooperation.

We are of the opinion that the management of the construction process in the regions on the basis of quality, competitive and effective service based on international standards is becoming the most fundamental task of today in the construction network that such a process can be carried out only through a cluster.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "The cluster is beneficial to the people, provides people with work, income. This is our biggest goal" [2].

Clusters are a group of interconnected companies in certain networks, specialized suppliers, service providers, firms in related networks and organizations related to their activities (for example, universities for Standardization, scientific research and project institutes, agencies trading associations), which are grouped by geographical designation [3].

"Clusters are able to embody a new and complementary way of understanding this-public policy. Understanding the state of clusters in certain regions will ensure the internal characteristics of the economic production potential of clusters as well as the limitations that exist for their future development" [4].

The establishment of clusters focused on the area and foreign markets is one of the key aspects of increasing competitiveness in the construction network and is aimed at meeting the need for housing. In this regard, the cluster model of Porter is widely used today in the improvement of the economic process throughout the world as a means of increasing the competitiveness of the economy of a region or country [5].

"In the modern concept of economic entities, the traditional division of the economy by sectors or sectors has lost its importance, making the use of systems of interaction between firms and organizations, the formation of strategic alliances, the cluster approach the first issue" [6].

It was analyzed by researchers and scientists on the development of innovative activities based on the organization of the cluster. Our scientific research is based on the principles of studying the position of the cluster in the construction complex.

Methodology of the research. In the process of writing a scientific article, the usuals of systematic analysis of the implementation of scientific research, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative and trending analysis were used.

Also in this process, their statistical data was taken from official sources and used the scientific-theoretical views of famous economic scientists on the role of innovation in this area and their opinion.

Analysis and results. Construction is the most important branch of the economy. Its condition largely determines the level of development of society. The main purpose of construction cluster Enterprises is to update production funds, improve the social sphere, modernize, reconstruct and technically re-equip material goods.

The development of the construction cluster will have a positive impact on the economy of the Republic and regions and will become a founder of the penetration of financial resources.

Of particular importance is the cluster approach to the development of territories at the regional level in the context of global problems of the world economy, ensuring the flexibility, transparency of management mechanisms in this area.

When using a cluster in the further improvement of the construction process, it is necessary that we definitely take into account that the cluster has the following distinctive features:

1. The existence of “short (low) collections of cluster members is determined by the uniformity of the territorial distribution of companies (merger of sales networks, export orientation).
2. The high level of cooperation of the members of the cluster.
3. Innovative activism.
4. Technological interconnection of networks (in the cluster there are enterprises of different networks, but technologically interconnected).
5. Competition and cooperation.

But, M. According to Porter's cluster theory, clusters affect non-competitive wrestling in three ways [3].

1. Clusters contribute to an increase in the productivity of firms and networks of which they are members.
2. The cluster contributes to the creation of innovation and its effective implementation.
3. The cluster promotes the creation of new enterprises that support and ensure innovation and expand cluster boundaries.

The formation of a construction cluster makes it possible to carry out cluster initiatives, the goals of which are:

- alternative (optimization) relations between construction companies in the regions of the country that interact within the framework of the network and the inter-network value added chain;
- support of the manufacturing sectors of the construction complex;
- formation of mechanisms for effective management of the regional construction complex;
- creation of projects based on goals within a certain territory for the development of regional and production infrastructure;
- creation of joint projects within the framework of activities in order to form personnel policies and increase innovation;
- creation of joint management activities for the management and control of current projects.

We believe that the choice of a building complex as a clustering object depends on the following circumstances:

- the creation of a large number of large investment projects requires the construction of new capacities and production areas;
- the provision of housing for the population within the framework of various state projects contributes to the minimization of the social component of investment risks, the growth of consumption and labor potential;
- existing problems in the field of construction negatively affect the socio-economic development of regions, in general, the investment environment.
- the construction complex has always had an economic effect and serves to develop other sectors of the economy.

Thus, the formation and development of a cluster approach in a construction complex provides:

- implementation of a cost-effective and cost-effective system of construction of affordable housing on the basis of modern technologies, which allows the production of high-quality construction products and materials at affordable prices for the population;
- the validity of housing construction projects and the effective use of resources;
- increase the export of goods and services through the entry of construction companies into strategic interaction networks and the targeted promotion of construction products to international markets;
- to increase the investment attractiveness of the territories due to a clear definition of the economic image of the territory and thereby ensure the attraction of domestic and foreign investments in the economy;
- increase the innovative activity of organizations within the cluster due to increasing awareness of new technologies;
- to increase the effectiveness of the specialist training system due to the fact that the requirements and obligations for the qualifications of workers are clearly established by the construction companies participating in the cluster, as well as the availability of methods for training builders and special training programs that improve the quality of construction work;
- the development of small and medium-sized businesses in conditions of open competition due to the attraction of investments in the economy and the increased demand for modern developments.

The growth of revenues at the enterprises of the construction complex, the increase in the number of jobs and wages due to the increase in the volume of exports and, in general, products and services by cluster member companies, whose effective development strategies in the process of introducing innovations are constantly increasing in competitiveness, indicates an improvement in the effective management environment.

Thus, the introduction of the cluster method combines resources in the production of building materials, promotes the introduction of innovative resource-saving technologies and advanced construction methods, and also creates favorable conditions for solving the housing problem.

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Conclusions and suggestions. As a result, research on the situation in the construction complex suggests that it is necessary to increase the pace of development in the construction network, but many factors objectively limit the development of construction enterprises, and in order to activate the process of development of the industry, it would be advisable to establish a cluster development center in the region based on Effective cooperation between construction companies is possible only with the introduction of cluster activities.

In conclusion, it is necessary to note that, considering the essence of the cluster's position in the construction complex, we can conclude that this phenomenon reduces costs, allows you to grow in the domestic market and reach foreign markets, increases the level of wages, increases the quality of the construction product and its competitiveness.

Stable enterprises with good results and the core of the cluster will “pull” small and medium-sized companies after them, forcing UKAR to improve the quality of components and

equipment supplied to other construction enterprises. Creating cluster networks in construction can facilitate quick access to a new range of products. Also, cluster interaction of enterprises is considered more promising in the design of investments, since for an investor, the complex of organizations for the state or private investor is not individual objects that are more attractive, but systemic solutions, the implementation of which requires interaction.

One of the ways to overcome difficulties in the national economy in the current realities and conditions of the development of the economy is the development of a building complex – on the basis of a cluster system.

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